

METHODS OF DEVELOPING READINESS OF CHILDREN WITH DISABILITIES FOR EDUCATION IN THE EXCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the methods of forming and developing the readiness of children with disabilities for the educational process in the conditions of the exclusive education system from a scientific, theoretical and practical point of view. The study substantiates the pedagogical effectiveness of individual approach, differentiated education, gradual development, motivation and support, flexibility, and visual and interactive methods. It also highlights the role and importance of the exclusive educational environment in the process of developing readiness for education. The conclusions of the article are of practical importance in the activities of educators working with children with disabilities.

Introduction. Today, one of the pressing issues is the humanization of the education system, the organization of the educational process taking into account the individual capabilities and needs of each child. The exclusive education system is especially important in working with children with disabilities. Exclusive education serves to cover children with quality education, ensure their socialization, and develop their readiness for education, regardless of their physical or psychological condition.

In an inclusive education system, a child's readiness for learning is determined not only by the level of formation of knowledge, skills, and competencies, but also by their psychological state, motivation, ability to communicate, and capacity for independent activity. Therefore, effective preparation of children with disabilities for the educational process requires special pedagogical approaches, flexible methods, and a supportive learning environment.

Scientific and pedagogical research recognizes individual and differentiated approaches, step-by-step development, encouragement and support, as well as visual and interactive methods as effective tools for enhancing the learning readiness of children with disabilities. However, practice shows that the systematic and purposeful application of these methods in inclusive education settings remains a pressing issue.[1. p.14]

In this regard, the aim of this article is to analyze, from theoretical and practical perspectives, the methods for developing learning readiness among children with disabilities within the inclusive education system, to substantiate their pedagogical effectiveness, and to

develop scientific conclusions and recommendations aimed at improving the educational process.

The readiness of children with disabilities for education is determined not only by the level of knowledge and skills, but also by their motivation, psychological state, communication skills, and the ability to function independently. Therefore, the effective organization of this process in the exclusive education system requires special pedagogical approaches and methods.[2. P.42]

The issue of preparing children with disabilities for the educational process is widely covered in scientific and pedagogical literature. Researchers recognize an individual approach as the main factor in this process. It is emphasized that differential education, flexible methods, mechanisms of encouragement and support facilitate children's adaptation to educational activities.

Also, in studies conducted on exclusive education, the convenience of the educational environment, psychological safety and professional competence of the teacher are indicated as important factors in the development of educational readiness. The existing literature confirms the scientific validity of the methods proposed in this article.

This study used the methods of pedagogical observation, comparison, analysis and generalization. In the course of the study, the level of readiness for classes of children with disabilities receiving education in exclusive education conditions, their adaptation to the educational process and activity were studied. Based on the data obtained, effective methods for developing educational readiness were identified.[3. p.19]

The concept of educational readiness in the exclusive education system. Educational readiness is a set of knowledge, skills, competencies, psychological and social preparation necessary for a child to successfully master educational activities. In the exclusive education system, this process is organized in a way that is adapted to the individual capabilities of the child.

Individual and differentiated approach. An individual approach involves organizing the educational process taking into account the abilities, needs and level of development of each child. A differentiated approach serves to develop educational readiness by distributing educational tasks and types of activities in accordance with the capabilities of children.

Step-by-step development. The step-by-step development method allows children to gradually acquire knowledge and skills. Dividing complex tasks into simpler stages forms a sense of confidence in children with limited opportunities and strengthens educational readiness.

Encouragement and support. Motivation is one of the important factors in educational readiness. Encouragement and positive assessment increase children's self-confidence, increase interest in learning activities. Support stabilizes the child's psychological state.[4. p.21]

Adaptability and interactive methods. Adaptable teaching methods ensure that the content, pace and form of the lesson are adapted to the individual needs of the child. Visual materials, game technologies and interactive activities are effective in increasing the concentration of attention of children with disabilities and their readiness for learning.[5. p.34]

In conclusion, the development of the educational readiness of children with disabilities in the exclusive education system is a complex but important pedagogical process. An individual and differentiated approach, gradual development, encouragement, adaptability and the effective use of interactive methods increase the quality of the educational process. These methods develop not only children's knowledge and skills, but also their social activity and independent thinking. The results of the study can serve as a methodological basis for educators in the practice of exclusive education

References:

1. Abdullaeva D. Fundamentals of special pedagogy. – Tashkent, 2017.
2. Karimova L. Methodology of working with children with disabilities. – Tashkent, 2019.
3. Mirzaev A. Pedagogical foundations of individual illumination. – Namangan, 2018.
4. Tomlinson C. A. The Differentiated Classroom. – Alexandria: ASCD, 2014.
5. Florian L. Inclusive Pedagogy in Practice. – London: Routledge, 2017

